

Geo-Intelligent Handover and Dynamic Selection PR_x-DOP: Maximizing 5G UAV Positioning Accuracy in Complex Real Urban Areas

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Abstract—This study proposes an adaptive positioning algorithm for UAVs in real urban 5G networks, leveraging existing cellular infrastructure with a practical approach. Unlike previous studies that rely on idealized scenarios, this work addresses the challenges of operating in real-world environments, where networks are designed for cellular coverage rather than positioning. The algorithm combines Received Signal Power (PR_x) with the Dilution of Precision (DOP) from base stations to optimize dynamic station selection, improving system geometry and reducing estimation errors. To predict the UAV's future position and calculate DOP in real-time, Kalman filters with Interacting Multiple Models (IMM), based on Constant Acceleration (CA) and Constant Velocity (CV) models, are employed. Additionally, a least squares approach with Taylor expansion, complemented by Tikhonov regularization, mitigates errors arising from ill-conditioned matrices. The methodology is applied to a predefined clustering of base stations in the city of Valencia (Spain), where each cluster is analyzed and optimized. The impact of the handover threshold on system accuracy is studied, proposing an inter-cluster handover scheme based on centroids. Experimental results obtained in a real urban environment demonstrate that the hybrid model significantly improves accuracy in handover zones compared to approaches relying solely on PR_x.

Index Terms—Positioning, UAV, 5G, Handover, MLAT, gNB selection, PR_x, DOP, IMM filter, Tikhonov regularization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The precise positioning of UAVs is a fundamental challenge in urban environments, particularly given their increasing demand for logistics, surveillance, and telecommunications applications. The GNSS is the predominant solution. However, its performance can be compromised in dense urban areas due to obstructions and being vulnerable to spoofing attacks [1]. In light of these limitations, 5G cellular network infrastructure emerges as a viable alternative, as its widespread deployment

and the availability of reference signals, such as the Positioning Reference Signal (PRS), enable the implementation of advanced positioning techniques.

Multilateration (MLAT) techniques for UAV positioning can be applied to 5G networks. This relies on techniques such as Time of Arrival (TOA) and Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA), which can provide accurate location estimates without depending on GNSS [2]. However, new challenges arise since cellular networks were not originally designed for this purpose. These include optimizing the selection of base stations (gNBs), minimizing errors in position estimation, and efficiently managing handovers between stations. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring reliable and precise positioning in complex urban environments.

In this context, this work proposes a hybrid positioning model based on the dynamic selection of base stations, considering two main approaches: one that relies solely on the Received Signal Power (PR_x) and another that integrates both PR_x and Dilution of Precision (DOP) to optimize system geometry and reduce estimation errors. The methodology is applied to a predefined clustering of base stations, where each cluster is analyzed and optimized based on metrics such as DOP and the Cramér-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB). Additionally, the impact of the handover threshold on system accuracy is studied, proposing an inter-cluster handover scheme based on centroids. This approach enhances position estimation by considering signal power and the geometric arrangement of base stations within and between clusters, resulting in more efficient and precise transitions between clusters.

To improve positioning robustness, Interactive Multiple Model (IMM) filters based on Constant Acceleration (CA) and Constant Velocity (CV) models are incorporated. These filters enable the prediction of the UAV's future location and the optimization of base station selection. Finally, Tikhonov

regularization addresses ill-conditioning issues in position estimation, particularly in areas with unfavorable geometry.

Testing is conducted in an urban environment based on the cellular network of the city of Valencia (Spain), where two realistic trajectories are evaluated. Different base station selection strategies are compared, analyzing the similarity between the generated clusters and the stations used. The results demonstrate that the hybrid model significantly improves accuracy in handover zones, where traditional approaches relying solely on PRx tend to produce more significant errors.

II. METHODOLOGY

The developed system proposes using 5G networks as an alternative or complement to GNSS, which exhibit vulnerabilities and limitations in urban environments for precise positioning. The network analyzed in this study is an existing cellular network in Valencia (Spain), covering a simulated area with 92 gNBs. These stations are assumed to have 5G technology and communicate using PRS. The gNBs transmit these signals to the Core Network (CN), where the necessary calculations and algorithms are executed to determine the position.

The positioning of devices within a 5G network is achieved through radio signal-based localization techniques, which precisely determine the user equipment's (UE) location. There are various positioning techniques, one of the most basic being Cell-ID, which relies on the coverage area of a base station to determine the device's location. However, this technique has limitations in terms of accuracy, prompting the development of more advanced methods such as TOA and TDOA [2].

The scenario is developed as an improvement over a previous study [3], where the distribution of gNBs in Valencia was determined using Machine Learning (ML) techniques because, from the point of view of performance, it is not possible to use the total number of gNBs to determine the position of UAVs. In consequence, the study divides the 92 gNBs into K clusters, specifically 7 clusters, each containing a different number of gNBs (using the k-means algorithm). Fig. 1 illustrates the clustering result and the trajectories generated to emulate the realistic flight of UAVs. These trajectories were created using the PX4 autopilot software-in-the-loop (SITL) environment [4].

Two trajectories were selected to analyze the system's behavior under conditions involving handover procedures. Additionally, they serve to evaluate how the IMM filter predicts the UAV's position and how this prediction influences the selection of gNBs based on the PRx.

A. 5G Network Infrastructure, and signals for Positioning

a) Positioning in 5G: networks relies on techniques that utilize signals between gNBs and UE. While traditional methods such as Cell-ID offer limited accuracy, more advanced techniques, such as TOA and TDOA measurements, have significantly improved positioning precision. The 5G network consists of two main components: the Radio Access Network (RAN), which includes the gNBs, and the 5G-CN, which manages functions such as mobility and location management.

Fig. 1: Clustering and proposed Trajectories

The RAN is responsible for transmitting and receiving positioning signals, such as PRS, which are used to calculate the UAV's position. The 5G-CN, on the other hand, coordinates positioning requests and processes the data to determine the UAV's location.

b) 5G NR Signal Configuration and its Impact on Positioning: The flexibility of 5G NR (*New Radio*) allows for the adaptation of parameters such as numerology (μ) and subcarrier spacing (*SCS*) to optimize performance in different scenarios. In the case of positioning, PRS signals are organized into specific patterns called “Comb”, which prevent interference between gNBs and enable efficient transmission. Although 5G operates in two frequency ranges (FR1 and FR2) [2], this study focuses on configurations with μ equal to 0, as they provide a suitable balance between bandwidth and precision for positioning applications.

B. Proposal for Centroid-Based Handover

Since the system relies on clustering using ML techniques, developing a handover model that adapts to this scenario is necessary. To achieve this, it has been proposed to use the midpoints of each cluster, known as centroids, when employing the k-means algorithm. This approach is similar to conventional handover processes, based on thresholds to determine the station change. However, in this case, it is not a change between individual stations but between clusters. In our scenario, 7 clusters have been defined, and at each time instant, the distance between the UAV and the centroids of each cluster is calculated (1).

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where i represents the coordinates for the different centroids of each cluster, and j represents the value of the coordinates for the UAV in the actual or predicted position. Based on this, it is possible to determine the handover in two ways:

a) *Hard Handover*: In this approach, only the distance between the UAV and the centroids of the clusters is considered. The active cluster will be the one whose distance to the UAV is the smallest. This method limits the operation to a single cluster at a time: when the UAV approaches another cluster, the previous cluster is deactivated, and the new one is activated. Although this model reduces computational load and the number of active stations, it has limitations regarding positioning accuracy. Specifically, when the UAV is at the edges of a cluster, the DOP deteriorates, resulting in less precise position estimation. Additionally, this method does not leverage nearby stations in neighboring clusters that could provide better DOP, making it less suitable for high-precision applications.

b) *Soft Handover*: This model is more suitable for positioning applications as it improves accuracy. Unlike the hard handover, this approach does not ignore neighboring stations. Instead, when the UAV exceeds a predefined threshold, stations from adjacent clusters are activated without deactivating those in the current cluster. Once the UAV leaves the handover zone, only the current cluster is used again. This method is particularly useful at the edges of clusters, where two or more clusters are activated to minimize errors in position estimation. To implement this approach, it is necessary to define an additional parameter: the threshold percentage. This value is calculated based on the average distance between all pairs of centroids, following the equation:

$$\bar{d} = \frac{2}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n d_{i,j} \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{d} represents the average distance between all centroids, ensuring a uniform handover zone for all clusters. This value, expressed in meters, is multiplied by the selected threshold percentage. The result is the decision threshold for the handover.

C. Position Estimation Techniques

To determine the coordinates X , Y , and Z of a UAV, the following algorithms and methods are employed in this study:

a) *Kalman Filter and Interacting Multiple Model*: This study implements the IMM filter using the Kalman Filter (KF) as its core estimator, incorporating CA and CV maneuver models. The IMM filter predicts the UAV's position, accounting for dynamic changes in its trajectory [5]. This predicted position is the initial input for the gNB and cluster selection process, enabling the system to anticipate and adapt to the UAV's movements. The IMM's output is critical as it provides the estimated position that drives the subsequent stages of the positioning system.

b) *Least Squares, Taylor Expansion, and Tikhonov Regularization*: A key component of the MLAT-based positioning system is the conversion of TDOA measurements into precise X , Y , and Z coordinates. The process begins with the Schaub-Robinson algorithm, which provides an initial position estimate. This estimate is then refined using a Taylor expansion

to improve accuracy. To address ill-conditioning issues that may arise from noisy or inconsistent measurements, Tikhonov regularization is applied. This regularization technique stabilizes the solution, mitigating errors caused by measurement inaccuracies and ensuring robust position estimation [6].

c) *Angle of Arrival (AoA)*: While the methods mentioned earlier provide accurate X and Y coordinates, the estimation of the Z axis (altitude) often contains significant errors. To address this limitation, AoA measurements are introduced as a complementary technique. AoA enhances the accuracy of the altitude estimation [7], particularly in scenarios where vertical precision is critical. By integrating AoA data, the system achieves a more comprehensive and reliable position estimation, especially in urban or complex environments where altitude errors are more pronounced.

D. Dynamic Selection of Base Stations

The selection of gNBs is a critical component of the proposed positioning system, as it determines the accuracy and reliability of position estimates. This process relies on two main metrics: the PRx and the DOP, which evaluate the system's geometry. The procedure to obtain the best gNBs depends on a predefined value of desired gNBs that will transmit the PRS signals. This value is provided as an input, and for this study, it is fixed at numSelectedBS of 9 [3] The procedure is as follows:

a) *Calculation of PRx*: For each UAV, the PRx from each active base station is calculated. The PRx is derived from the signal attenuation due to path loss, using the UMi model [8] for this scenario. The path loss depends on the distance between the UAV and the base station and the operating frequency. The received signal power is expressed as $PRx = P_{tx}/10^{PL/10}$, where P_{tx} is the transmitted power, and PL is the path loss in decibels (dB). Selecting the best PRx values helps reduce estimation errors, as these signal measurements correspond to the UAV's actual position. This step acts as an initial filter, identifying the base stations with the strongest signals near the UAV, which are then evaluated for their DOP.

b) *Evaluation of Geometry*: DOP is a metric that assesses the impact of the geometric arrangement of the base stations relative to the UAV. On the positioning error, a low DOP value indicates a favorable geometry, resulting in more accurate position estimates. The DOP is evaluated using the Jacobian matrix J , which describes the sensitivity of the range measurements to changes in the UAV's position. The DOP is then computed as $Q = (J^T J)^{-1}$, and the final DOP value is obtained as $DOP = \sqrt{\text{trace}(Q)}$. This formulation provides an intuitive interpretation of how the positioning accuracy is affected by the base station geometry.

c) *Hybrid Selection Algorithm with a Greedy Approach*: The hybrid selection algorithm combines PRx and DOP to select the most suitable base stations. A greedy approach evaluates base station combinations to optimize performance and reduce computational complexity. This approach is implemented in the following steps:

Algorithm 1 Hybrid PRx-DOP Selection

- 1: **PRx Pre-selection:** Sort base stations by PRx and select the top N candidates.
 - 2: **DOP Evaluation:** Iteratively add the station that best improves DOP until reaching numSelectedBS.
 - 3: **Final Selection:** If no set meets the DOP threshold, select those minimizing DOP; otherwise, choose the highest PRx stations within the threshold.
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The Algorithm 2 describes the procedure for obtaining the positioning and the operation of the proposed system. The process begins by identifying the UAV's initial position using Cell-ID, which determines the cluster where the UAV is located. This initial position is the starting point for selecting gNBs to transmit the PRS. Subsequently, the TOA value is calculated to estimate the UAV's position. A value greater than 3 is required to activate the IMM filter, as three initial positions are needed to determine and manage the CV and CA maneuver models.

Algorithm 2 UAV Tracking Procedure

Procedure Tracking

Init Tracking

while true do

Predict UAV Position

Select gNBs based on PRx - DOP

Calculate TOAs - TDOAs

Estimate Position using LS, Taylor, and Regularization

if Estimated Positions > 3 **then**

Init IMM and KF

end if **if** Is the UAV flight ending? **then**

End Tracking

Break **end if****end while**

Additionally, as the UAV moves through the area and approaches the borders of clusters, the Handover procedure is activated. This process for activating or deactivating clusters uses the position estimated by the IMM filter.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

To evaluate the performance, the following 5G signal parameters were used: a frequency of 3.5 GHz, a UMi pathloss model, a μ of 0, a comb spacing of 6, a fixed UAV altitude of 100 meters, a synchronization error of 65 ns [9], and handover thresholds set at 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%. The trajectory samples were collected every 5 s. All simulations were conducted using Monte Carlo trials with 100 iterations.

The results of gNB and cluster selection, based on the IMM-predicted trajectory, are summarized in Table I. For both trajectories, cluster selection achieves 100% similarity when compared to the real trajectory, demonstrating the IMM filter's effectiveness in predicting cluster transitions. However,

differences arise in gNB selection. Trajectory 1 achieves a station similarity of 99.03%, while Trajectory 2 shows a slightly lower similarity of 96.17%. These discrepancies indicate that, although the IMM filter accurately predicts cluster transitions, minor inaccuracies in position estimation lead to suboptimal gNB selection at specific points. This highlights the importance of refining position prediction models, such as incorporating advanced dynamic models (e.g., the Singer model), to further improve gNB selection accuracy.

TABLE I: Comparison of total gNBs and Cluster Similarity

Trajectories	Station Similarity (%)	Cluster Similarity (%)
Trajectory 1	99.03	100.00
Trajectory 2	96.17	100.00

The next step is to compare how the model proposed by considering PRx + DOP could be more efficient in terms of CRLB, whereas shown in Fig.2 is presented the CRLB heat maps generated under two different approaches for gNBs selection in a positioning scenario based on PRS signals.

(a) PRx only

(b) PRx-DOP

Fig. 2: CRLB.

Fig.2a shows the model where the base station selection is performed solely based on the PRx. It can be seen that

although a low CRLB is achieved in some regions, there are several areas with high values, indicating a lower accuracy in position estimation. This suggests that, although receiving power is an important criterion, it cannot guarantee an optimal distribution of base stations regarding positioning accuracy. The second Fig.2b represents the improved model, where the selection of base stations combines the PRx with the DOP. In this case, a significant reduction in CRLB values is observed over a large part of the map, indicating a substantial improvement in positioning accuracy. Compared to the PRx-only model, this hybrid approach achieves a better distribution of selected base stations, minimizing areas of high uncertainty.

Figure 3 analyzes the impact of handover percentage on positioning accuracy. For XY error, both trajectories show reduced RMSE as handover increases, with Trajectory 1 improving by 1 meter when raising handover from 5% to 15%. Beyond 15%, gains diminish, stabilizing at 16 meters RMSE. Trajectory 1 initially exhibits higher error (≈ 1.5 meters) at 5% handover due to proximity to cluster edges with poor DOP, but this gap narrows as handover increases. Dynamic station selection based on PRx and DOP optimizes accuracy by prioritizing geometry over signal strength.

Fig. 3: Handover for different percentages and its impact on proposed trajectories

For Z error (altitude), AoA measurements enhance accuracy, particularly at higher handover percentages, as neighboring clusters with AoA-capable stations are included. The com-

bined TDOA and AoA model ensures that XY improvements indirectly refine height estimation, although AoA remains unaffected by synchronization errors.

A 15% handover is recommended, balancing accuracy and network efficiency. Synchronization errors (65 ns) remain a limitation, impacting MLAT-based positioning precision.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The hybrid PRx-DOP approach effectively reduces UAV positioning errors by optimizing base station selection, maintaining high accuracy despite minor discrepancies at specific locations. The integration of advanced techniques, such as the IMM filter, enhances system reliability, while future research could explore additional motion models (e.g., Singer) to further improve performance. By incorporating DOP, the model avoids stations with strong signals but poor geometry, reducing positioning uncertainty, particularly in urban environments. However, MLAT's sensitivity to synchronization errors remains a limitation, necessitating advanced clock synchronization. A 15% handover threshold balances accuracy and network efficiency, with adaptive clustering offering potential for further optimization.

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